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SUSTAINABLE CHANGES BEYOND COVID-19 FOR A SECOND SEMESTER PHYSICS COURSE FOR ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The course Physics for Electrical Engineering is part of the curriculum of the bachelor program Electrical Engineering at University of Applied Science Aachen. Before covid-19 the course was conducted in a rather traditional way with all parts (lecture, exercise and lab) face-to-face. This teaching approach changed fundamentally within a week when the covid-19 limitations forced all courses to distance learning. All parts of the course were transformed to pure distance learning including synchronous and asynchronous parts for the lecture, live online-sessions for the exercises and self-paced labs at home. Using these methods, the course was able to impart the required knowledge and competencies. Taking the teacher's observations of the student's learning behaviour and engagement, the formal and informal feedback of the students and the results of the exams into account, the new methods are evaluated with respect to effectiveness, sustainability and suitability for competence transfer. Based on this analysis strong and weak points of the concept and countermeasures to solve the weak points were identified. The analysis further leads to a sustainable teaching approach combining synchronous and asynchronous parts with self-paced learning times that can be used in a very flexible manner for different learning scenarios, pure online, hybrid (mixture of online and presence times) and pure presence teaching.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Physics module before covid-19 crisis

At the faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology physics is a second semester module with 7 ECTS for the electrical engineering students. Main topics of the module are mechanics, thermodynamics, optics, waves and solid state physics. According to the curriculum it consists of 4 lessons lecture, 2 lessons exercise and 1 lesson lab per week and up to 120 students participate each summer term (one lesson corresponds to 45 minutes). In addition to the 7 lessons per week the students should work for another 7 hours at home for learning, preparing,

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exercising and wrap-up. Before the covid-19 crisis the module was conducted in a traditional way. Besides the experimental work also reports are part of the labs. During lectures some activating elements were included like live experiments and demos and online quizzes. ILIAS was used to distribute the learning material [1].

1.2 Ad-hoc change to online teaching

During March 2020 – the beginning of the covid-19 crisis in Germany – the situation for the summer term starting end of March was unclear. No efforts were spent at that time to prepare an online semester – a great misjudgement. One week before the start of the summer term it was decided by politics and university administration to change the semester to pure online mode. Therefore, just one week remained to find a suitable solution and setup to run the module without any face-to-face elements.

2 METHODOLOGY

Based on department internal discussions and strong support by the IT department it was decided for all modules of the department to use Webex Training to replace the face-to-face elements. The concrete setup of how to integrate this video conference tool dedicated for online trainings was up to each module. For the physics module the ad-hoc setup was a mixture of synchronous and asynchronous elements and communication channels to enable an activating learning style using inverted classroom methods with distance learning, similar to Ref. [2], to focus on the discussions about the content during the live online sessions:

- **Lecture:** The lecture changed to distance learning with an inverted classroom approach ([3], [4]), the slides were completed with an audio track to form rather short (up to 30 to 40 minutes) learning units. Videos from the live experiments were included in these units for visualization and basis for explanations. These learning units were uploaded to ILIAS using a date based folder structure for better orientation of the students. During the synchronous live sessions via Webex training the content of the corresponding units were discussed and the integrated quiz supported the students to control their learning success.
- **Exercise:** The exercises were conducted synchronously during online live sessions to enable discussions about the approaches, unclear methods and solutions of the exercises or other questions.
- **Lab:** The lab was purely asynchronous. Therefore, simply using inverted classroom like in [5] was not possible. Also a transfer from experiments to pure written work like in [6] was not suitable for the learning target. Two new experiments were developed – one using a pendulum, one using a rolling element – in such a manner that these experiments can be conducted by the students at home in groups of two using just basic sensors of a smartphone and some basic material. The reports for both experiments were uploaded to ILIAS, corrected and returned to the students until the report was correct.
- **Communication:** As the pure online execution of the module was new to both lecturer and students, several communication channels were set up, for

instance synchronous communication during the live sessions, and asynchronous communication via mail and a Webex Teams group. In addition the students used Whatsapp for their communication.

3 EVALUATION, DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The evaluation was done in several steps, a self-designed online survey during the semester, the official evaluation and own observations of the lecturer.

3.1 Online survey during the semester

The self-designed online survey took place 6 weeks after the start of the semester. Main purpose of this survey was to check whether the ad-hoc setup of the module works for the students or not. 32 students participated and main results of this survey are listed in Table 1. From suggestions by the students a detailed plan for the lecture as well as an optimized file size for the learning material were taken into account. All communication channels were used. Main drawbacks of the current setup were the missing live sessions at the campus and the distraction of attention at home.

Table 1. Summary of main results of self-designed online survey and the evaluation (1: very good; 5: very bad or 1: much to high; 3: fitting; 5: much to low for workload)

Question	Online survey	Evaluation
How satisfied are you with the module?	1.8	1.5 (1.6)
How is the structure?	---	1.6 (1.5)
How is your learning success?	---	1.8 (2.3)
Does the setup supports self-learning?	---	1.6 (---)
How is responsiveness of lecturer	1.3	1.2 (1.4)
What about the workload?	---	2.5 (---)

3.2 Evaluation at the end of the semester

The formal evaluation took place at the end of the semester with 30 participants. Even though the sample size is again rather low, the results were used for analysis and main results are also listed in Table 1. For comparison the average results of previous years are given in brackets. Compared to the online survey both satisfaction and responsiveness improved at the end of the semester. Compared with previous years there is just a slight difference for structure, satisfaction and responsiveness whereas the learning success improved significantly. Considering that the evaluation survey differs both from the online survey and the survey from previous years, this results shows at least that the online module maintained its results and could improved the learning success – at least for the participants. Main topics of the written feedback were problems with the lab at home including the report and again the missing live session at campus (Fig. 1).

3.3 Lecturer's observations

Both lecturer and students adapted quickly to the new teaching format. After some technical issues and lacking experience in the beginning the setup with synchronous and asynchronous parts worked very well (Fig. 1). During the live sessions fruitful discussions evolved, even to a higher extent compared to live sessions during normal semesters, demonstrating highly motivated participants. On the other hand just about 40 % of students joined the synchronous sessions. Hence a majority failed to attend the live sessions. Unofficial feedback was both missing motivation and self-organization as well as satisfaction with the learning material provided via ILIAS. The lab ran rather well, but the iterations until the final report was higher compared to the previous years. Even though several communication channels were used it was difficult for many students to find and build their own study groups. The average result of the final exam corresponded very well with the results from the previous years (2020: 3.2; 2015-2019: 2.8-3.6).

Die angebotenen Formate der Veranstaltung versetzten mich in die Lage, Inhalte selbstständig zu vertiefen.

Die eingesetzten Lernformate und -werkzeuge haben eine ausreichende Kommunikation mit der/dem Lehrenden ermöglicht.

Livelehrveranstaltungsformate wie Videokonferenz oder Webinare

Interaktion

- Die Webex-Konferenzen haben sehr gut funktioniert
- es wäre besser einen direkten Kontakt zu haben
- Eine Präsenzveranstaltung fehlt
- es wäre besser einen direkten Kontakt zu haben

Abschließende Bemerkungen

- Alles in allem war/ bin ich sehr zufrieden. Trotzdem finde ich das Praktikum nicht optimal.
- Das Praktikum ist meiner Meinung nach deutlich zu hart bewertet.

Fig. 1. Extract of some results of the formal evaluation

4 IMPROVEMENTS AND SUSTAINABILITY

Several improvements were taken into account to increase the learning success for the students and to convert the ad-hoc setup into a sustainable format with a high degree of flexibility for on-site and online sessions. The structure for the lecture and the exercise was not changed as this inverted classroom setup with asynchronous and synchronous parts provided a clear structure for the students and improved the quantity and quality of debates about the contents. This format also allows a high degree of flexibility with regard to online or live sessions at the campus. More sophisticated quizzes and additional videos are introduced to increase activation of

the students. Also the lab can be easily switched from online to on-site execution to adopt to the overall situation. Additional training sessions to improve the writing skills for the reports are introduced. For the whole department a dedicated team building forum is implemented in ILIAS.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Despite the challenges of the ad-hoc change to a pure online semester the implemented setup turned out to be rather successful. In addition, it forced the implementation of new learning methodologies. To transfer this setup into a sustainable and flexible setup the evaluation and feedback from summer term 2020 were taken into account. The new setup, which is used in summer term 2021 with unclear perspective whether on-site sessions will be possible, shows a high degree of flexibility for online and on-site teaching and incorporates elements of the inverted classroom concept wherever suitable. The author thanks the IT department for strong support during the ad-hoc transition to online teaching including excellent tools, suitable IT infrastructure and fast and helpful responses to any inquiry.

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